

DESIGN THE LEARNING EXPERIENCE WITH THE HELP OF TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

We learn the different experiences in different situations for the whole life from birth, life can be called a kind of journey of learning experience. We gain time to time different experiences regarding different concepts or the single one. Learning experiences has no time or age limits. It can happen or occur anytime. It can be academic or non-academic. Learnings can take place even from a child as well as from the adult one. It can prove itself as a boon for all of us. We learn experiences from the starting point of our life till the ending point.

Key words – *Learning Experience, design or model of learning experience, Technology*

Introduction - Learning means that you experience the situation, deal with that situation. We come to know it's both sides whether is crucial or beneficial. Sometimes we receive it from others and also we can provide it to others. IN context of Education, it can be a fruitful thing to the learners in any discipline. It can help them in understanding the concepts. It can help an instructor to make effective the instructions. Designing learning experiences or a model of learning experiences is a live step for the welfare of the learners. Even for it, we can take the experiences or the views of the instructors, the seniors, the parents and the most important the learners itself. For designing a learning experience model , first of all , it is mandatory to know the basics, we have to construct for, it's importance ,implications, steps etc. , we have the follow, the purpose to prepare the design of LX (Learning Experience) .

Learning Experience – learning experiences can also be called “**Experiential Learning**”. When we get learnings through facing the situation directly or moreover, learning by doing. Learnings
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may be in class-room or outside if the school. It can be in context of academic qualification or real life concepts.

Learning experiences play a significant role in our life . It Forms an impact that brings fruitful outcomes to the learner. As one practise it by itself , it leaves an unforgettable impression on the learners mind.

Any experience we learn from a particular situation, is called , learning experience. It can have both aspects whether good or bad, long lasting or for a little moment. Not only this ,but it can be natural or artificial also.

As in schools, science laboratory is established to learn experience by doing hand on activities . Whereas in real life practical situations provides you life skills. In both cases we get learning experiences and shares with others when needed or receives when demanded.

Learning experiences , in context of education are mostly planned. Planned to achieve some particular objectives, in a particular stream, for a particular learner, with a particular strategy, in a particular time, with a particular expected outcomes.

Learning Experiences Design : As we discussed above, Learning Experience Design should be in accordance with the needed one. First of all , when design learning experience, the context should be kept in mind and as talking about **Education** , the stream or discipline is an important thing to be noticed sothat a base can be prepared for that .

Among all this, picking views from sources would be the first job Taking important points in notice we design LXD (Learning Experience Design).

Purpose – Designing learning experience should be purposeful in accordance with the need of the learner .whether it is academic or non academic technical or non technical, theortical or practical etc. .

Purpose of learning experience design or model should be on providing the training in a simplest and easiest manner.

It should be honest about providing a solid base structure regarding learnings to the learners.

Need- Learning Experience Design should recognize the needs of the trainees or the learner .Infact, it has to be concerned about the needs of parents, the trainers, the administrators, the financers, the producers as well as consumers , the managers etc.

It should fulfil the needs of society overall .

No doubt , LXD (Learning Experience Design) is responsible to satisfy the needs at a grand level i.e. National as well International .

This design or model has to move with the respect of the universal concepts.

Simple and Easy – LXD (Learning Experience Design) must possess qualities of being simple and easy. It should not be a complex process.

The trainees or the learner should not be bounded to the chains of complexities.

They should not be over burdened with the instructions or guidelines to be followed . The learners should be provided an environment that nourishes them in a pleasant manner .The learner’s mind must be peaceful regarding the processing of the LXD(Learning Experience Design).The learner should experience the learnings with peace at mind not hurriedly.

Flexibility - learning experience should be designed with the option of flexibility. It should not be so rigid if some changes are required.

Learning experience design should be so flexible to get changes randomly. The changes must be done in accordance with the needs of the learner or the trainees.

Up-To-Date – Learning Experience Design should be updated time to time with the use of latest strategy, skills, technology.

It should follow the system that is new and full of fascility. Learning Experience Design should be so that it must be go through the recent updates regarding learning matters or materials.

Interaction - Learning Experience Design should be in accordance with the interaction i.e. interaction of the learner and instructor, instructor and the parents, parents and the administrators, administrators and the financers,producers etc.

Overall, the whole stakeholders should be in interaction with each other.

Hand- on -activities- Success of the (LXD) Learning Experience Design depends on doing the activities by hand or by the learner itself. Such type of learning lasts for a long time.

It leaves an impact something like that you can form a strong base for the learning as you have practice it by your own hand.

It provides you to learn the concepts practically.

Adequate and appropriate practice - Practice makes a man perfect. So it is only and only the practice that can lead the learner towards the success. The Learning Experience Design should make the learner or the trainee to practice more and more , not in the manner of cramming something but likely to achieve perfection honestly.

Strategic – Learning Experience Design should be based on the qualities in favour of the proper strategies related to the learner or the trainee one.

It should be according to the learner's present existing knowledge or physical and mental capacities etc.

A learning Experience Design should follow the strategy that is convenient to the parents and the whole society.

Creative and Amusing – Learning Experience Design should be interesting as well as Creative also. The learners should enjoy the environment of learnings.

They should be free of boredom of the repetition or the drilling to the concepts overtime.

Design Learning Experience With The Help Of Technology - Success at a grand level of a Learning Experience Design(LXD) depends upon the most ,choosing the right technology, whether it is online or offline.

We have so many options to make the design run at an average speed in context of the technology . Internet, multimedia telecommunications, Personal computers, Smartboard, such devices helps a lot in connecting the learner from different directions.

The technology brings the learners or the trainees together to the same platform and unite them with the same process of the Learning Experience Design (LXD).

Technology is the tool , without that the design can not move even a single step. Technology is exactly like a track on which the engine of (LXD) Learning Experience Design can run smoothly .Use of technology or to take the help of technology mandatory as well as self -desired also. With the help of technology , we can convert the time taking process into the lesser one process.

Technology should be reasonable and affordable for each and every kind of the learners or the trainees . It should be convenient and in the reach of every learner and instructor.

But , it is necessary to keep a watch alerting against the misuse of the technology. Misuse in the sense, the technology for the LXD's processing should be used only for online classes or virtual environment.

Time to time the design, has to be interacted to each and every learner.

Use of technology must be in the time limit sessions so that the learners or the trainees must not be habitual of it.

Moreover, the learners should be provided opportunities for the face to face interactions for the whole academy. Technology must be used that it could not affect or harm anyone at any level i.e. physical, mental, psychological or societal etc.

Among all that, it is compulsory to make or choose the right technology ,convinient to all. It's cost, side effects all should be taken in care for the sake of the learners .

Any tool of technology or electronic device or gadget should be able to provide a quality of service whether it is in the classroom or at a distant point.

Therefore, it is important to choose the technology or to make the right use of technology sothat it can not create any hurdles or problems to the learners in their conceptual processing.

Challenges to Design the Learning Experience - When we design the learning experience model, so many things are to keep in notice for the better sake of the all of the stakeholders.

It can be a little problematic to bring all the learners at same platform in one time.Needs of the learners can differ from one another regarding the same concept.

Sometime the learning design model can be a failure if the needs are not considered properly. To fulfil the requirements of the trainees can be difficult by a single design or model.

It matters a lot when designing the learning experience, the age level , the social background, the maturity level and the confidence level of the trainees.

And if we talk in context of the right choice of technology, it may be quite possible that the learners can not afford the high quality of technology .

The learner may not be able to pay for the equipments used in the processing of learning Experience design. Sometimes the cost is too high to afford it for the trainees.

Except it , how can be a Learning Experience Design (LXD) beneficial for the all of the administrators, financers, producers, instructors, society etc.

It needs to do work sincerely to satisfy the needs of all the important member involved in the Learning Experience Design.

Among all this, it is also to keep in mind that the use of technology may affect the learners physically as well as mentally.

Working unnecessarily with the internet, can be harmful to the learners. Working a lot, can cause headache, loss of eyesight, Fatigue, weakness loss if interest, boredom etc.

Too much use of technology may affect the learner psychologically as well. Even sometime, the one can be seen talking to someone uninterestingly. He may feel disinterested in other societal contexts.

So, it is necessary to control the excessive use of modern equipments of technology. And to make the classes more interactive with the instructor.

Implications of Learning Experience – In spite of all the challenges, Learning Experience Design is prepared for best the learnings to be provided to the learners .

Keeping in mind, all the necessities in context of a particular course or even general, whether it is theoretical or practical .

Regarding any of the stream i.e. Arts, Science, Maths, Commerce, Medical or Non-Medical etc. both for the online or offline mode, it is of great significance.

It is implicable as it facilitates not only the learners or the trainees but also takes care of the comforts or discomforts of the guardians of the learners.

Their social, economic status , concessions in the fee structure, providing experienced faculty, Making use of latest technology, a cheerful environment, classes free of rigid discipline, Cooperative learning strategies, learnings with Collaboration etc.

Moreover, it works for the values or ethics, social norms to be inherited in the learner's nature to work with a sense of cooperation, adjustment, patience, determination, Positive outlook, balancing the surroundings, brotherhood from a small scale to grand scale.

It broadens the thinking process, includes the hands on activities, opportunities for the learners to create of their own. Appreciation of the ideas or suggestions from each and every ward.

Learning Experience Design or model is based on Conceptual aspects of the learners or their course work.

It completes its steps by collecting precious views of the expertise and then analyzed its standards from the view point of the trainees.

Even If felt something left, or to add an important step to be taken the whole cycle is to be revised again to bring it to the learners with a perfect design or model.

Thus , Learning Experience Design is a fruitful production of the hard work done by the ones who have experienced the situation . And recognizes the demands of the learners or the trainees in accordance with the time, space and money etc.

Conclusion : On behalf of above writing, it is quite clear that Learning Experience proves itself to be a boon for all of us in general life or routine work. Sometimes we receive these experiences from others or sometimes gives it to others. In both cases, learning experiences prevents us to repeat the mistakes again or helps us to do the job correctly. In context Education, Learning Experience or Learning Experience Design is such a tool or technique that paves the way for the learners or trainees, it not only guides the trainees regarding their course or studies but also makes a kind of security to their future. By stepping the way, made by the Learning Experience Design (LXD), learners , no doubt can add a valuable shine or bright to their carrer and life also.

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